

EMPLOYEE LOCATION TRACKING SYSTEM

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Abstract:

Disruption tolerant networks (DTNs) are defined by low node density, unpredictable node mobility, and lack of global network information. The majority of present research in DTNs focus on data forwarding, but only limited work has been done on efficient data access to mobile users. In this paper, we propose a new system that enables to track even in Disruption tolerant Network, thus it is possible to track even when the network connection is disrupted/not continuous. In DTNs the recent location of the nodes and their movement can be tracked using the Pulsecounting and Probetracking method, with this information the current location of the employee is found.

Keywords- *Disruption Tolerant Networks, Node mobility, Data forwarding, Pulsecounting and Probtracking*

Introduction

Now a days, large number of location depend applications are available to the users. Most of this work on GPS. GPS is used for tracking the locations of place that are nearby or far away. This is only possible when the user has a stable i.e., continuous network connection. We use this method to track an employee. As we are tracking an employee it should be continuous without any disruption thus a new technique is added with the current. This technique helps to track in Disruption Tolerant Networks (DTNs). In this paper we use this method to track the employee's location. This method is slightly different from other usual types of tracking. This works without any connection or even when the signal is weak. By this technique we could transfer important data without the help of strong signal. In employee location tracking system (ELS), we track a

user's location using method like Pulsecounting and Probtracking. ELS application is useful were high value transactions done. In this system the admin can monitor each and every movements of employee. If the employee lost his way it is monitored by the admin and a correct route is sent to the employee. It also helps the admin to find the misbehavior of the user. As it works, even if the network signal is weak, because we use delay tolerant network.

Proposed System

This paper proposes a system that helps to track employees. Today there are many systems that helps to track but, most of these work when there is a continuous network connection. The method like Pulsecounting and a Probtracking are used to track the movement of mobile nodes of an employee. Pulsecounting calculates the number of walking steps of an employee using the accelerometer and decides the direction of each step using the electronic compass. Thus, able to form an estimation of current location. The encountering of phones equipped with GPS could be taken as a reference point. Probtracking detects the trajectory movements based on the partial location information reported by the other mobile nodes. A Markov chain is constructed using the movement history data. It is used to determine the most probable walking route of an employee, without the need for global location information in DTNs. Disruption tolerant networking (DTNs) is a technology enabling communication in networks with high delays periods of disruption. Thus, we are able to track an employee in delay tolerant network.

Advantages

- Possible to track even in Delay tolerant network
- Possible to track multiple employee
- Accuracy of direction mapping

Working

Our system "Employee Location Tracking" system of consists of five steps, as shown below.

- Initial locator
- Step counter

- Mapping of Directions
- Creation of Trajectory
- Place estimation

1. Initial Locator

As the first step, initial position of each node is found. After finding the initial position a map of this area will be downloaded to the employee's cell phone. We use the Google map. Since it provides an open access to its data and APs. The map is downloaded opportunistically when the device has a chance to access the internet.

2. Step Counter

In this method, we use the accelerometer to measure walking steps of the employee. The accelerometer records user movement in three dimensions: x (front and back), y (left and right), and z (up and down). We plot the accelerometer data of users with the cell phone putting in three different positions. And count the steps.

3. Mapping of Directions

Direction is an important phase of movement, which can be measured by electronic compass. The compass on the employee records the user's orientation in the form of an angle with respect to magnetic north. To make the data discrete we project the compass data to eight discrete directions north, northeast, east, southeast, south, southwest, west, and northwest.

Figure 1 the compass showing the direction of the employee's movement

4. Creation of Trajectory

With the results from step counter and direction mapping, we are able to describe user movement trajectories. A movement trajectory is defined as a series of segments with distance and direction.

5. Place estimation

Given a trajectory $t(p_0 \rightarrow p_1)$, if the location of departure point p_0 is known, we can roughly estimate the location of p_1 by accumulating the trajectory segments. We use the encounter opportunity of nodes to improve the estimation accuracy.

4. System Architecture

Figure 2 System architecture of Employee Location tracking system

Basic Components

- **Mobile client:** the mobile client consists of a mobile phone with a GPS receiver which can be used to find the location of the user.
- **Repository:** the repository consists of all the information about the users, location maps, and the location-related results.

- **Web client:** the information in the repository can be managed and viewed using the web client. The user receives the location information from the web client on their mobiles.
- **Map service:** the map service is an agent based which provides both the mobile and the web client with map data. The map service uses GPS to track the position of the user. The location information is updated to web client every time by the mobile phone.
- **Message alert system:** the message alert system deals with detecting position of user and update on server.

Conclusion And Future Enhancement

We proposed a new system to support tracking in DTNs. With the help of Pluscounting and Probtracking we estimate the location of the employee. With this system we are able to keep a track of the employee, also this helps to find the misbehaving employee. To make this system more secure we could implement it with the help of embedded system.

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